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POSSIBILITIES OF ANALYTICAL CONTINUATION OF POTENTIAL FIELDS

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Abstract

The article is devoted to possibilities analytical continuation of potential fields, the solution of which plays an important role in the geological interpretation of the observed anomalies in gravity and magnetic prospecting. The possibilities of analytical continuation of potential fields are analyzed on the example of the analytical continuation of the gravitational field from homogeneous geological bodies of a cylindrical shape located at a certain depth. As is known, the analytical continuation of fields refers to one of the methods for transforming gravimagnetic fields in order to separate fields into local and regional components. To implement the process of analytical continuation, the graphical and mathematical capabilities of the SURFER digital program are used.

Keywords: vertical gravity component, gravity model, two-dimensional cylinder, grid, digital modeling, analytical continuation, potential fields.

Introduction

The gravimetric and magnetic method of exploration, which is based on studying the distribution of potential fields, created by individual structural rock raisings with excessive density and magnetic intensity of the rocks, is of great importance in the process of exploration and study of the geological structure areas, promising for oil, gas and ore deposits.

At the stage of transformation of gravimagnetic data, a very important task is solved - the identification of local and regional anomalies, that are associated with the corresponding geological structures and bodies. There are various methods for transformation potential fields, among which an important role is played by the method of analytic continuation of fields in the upper and lower half-space [1-3,10-12,14-16]. As known at present, digital gravimeters and magnetometers are used in gravimagnetic survey, which measure the value of gravity and magnetic intensity with high accuracy. Therefore, the task of transformation is solved using modern graphics programs in two-dimensional and three-dimensional versions based on the results of computer calculations of modeling gravitational and magnetic fields using the developed algorithms and programs, which provides the most accurate field separation [4-9,13]. This explains the relevance of scientific research conducted in this direction. The purpose of these studies is analytic continuation of potential gravity fields for homogeneous geological bodies of cylindrical form.

Means and methods

The methods of analytic continuation of potential fields include the method of analytic continuation to the upper half-space with respect to the Poisson integral and the method of analytic continuation into the lower half-space using the Gauss formula and etc. The process of transformation is usually performed using developed algorithms and programs on a computer. Let perform

an analytical continuation of the gravitational field from two homogeneous two-dimensional cylinders, lying at a certain depth. As is known, the vertical component of gravity V_z from a horizontal circular cylinder is calculated by the formula:

$$V_z = \frac{2G\lambda h}{x^2 + h^2}, \quad (1)$$

Here G is the gravitational constant; λ is linear density of the cylinder, $[\lambda] = g / \text{sm}$; $\lambda = s \cdot \Delta\sigma$; $\Delta\sigma$ - the volume density; s - the cross-sectional area of a circular cylinder; $\lambda = \pi R^2 \Delta\sigma$; R is the radius of the cylinder, in units of km; h is the depth of the cylinder axis, in units of km; x is the coordinate of the observation point along the profile, in units of km.

For the case of two homogeneous horizontal cylinders, the formula for calculating the total gravimetric effect, taking into account the direction of the axes of the SURFER graphics program for the "Function" mode, will have the following form:

$$V_z = 2G\lambda(h+z) \left(\frac{1}{(x_1-x)^2+(h+z)^2} + \frac{1}{(x_2-x)^2+(h+z)^2} \right) \quad (2)$$

Here x_1 and x_2 are the abscissas of the centers of the horizontal cylinders; x is the abscissa of the observation point (calculation point); z is the height or depth of the analytical continuation of the gravitational (Fig. 1). The parameter z takes on a negative value, if it is performing the analytical continuation of the field to the lower half-space and a positive value, if it is performing the analytical continuation of the field to the upper half-space.

Let us take the radius of the two circular cylinders equal to 1 km, occurring at a depth of $h = 3$ km, located at a distance of 2 km from each other (distance between the centers of the cylinders) with excess density $\Delta\sigma =$

0, 2 g/sm³, that is typical of sedimentary deposits of the eastern part of the Middle Kura depression for Azerbaijan. Analytical continuation of the field of gravity will be performed using modern graphics programs. At present, the SURFER program, which allows not only to present the results obtained in a modern graphical interface, but also perform various mathematical calculations in the "Function" mode with the subsequent presentation of graphical results, is widely popular.

Results:

At the beginning, the analytical continuation of the gravity field was performed into the lower half-space. For this purpose, using the SURFER program in the "function" mode, the V_z values were calculated at different depths z , starting from zero (observation surface) to a depth of 6 km with a step of 0.5 km, as a result, it is obtained a "grid" of the calculated data, based on which, various maps were built in 2D and 3D versions. As can be seen from the presented drawings, the analytical continuation of the field into the lower half-space allows you to emphasize the "special points", associated with the sources of gravitational disturbances

in the modern interface of the graphical editor. The intensity of the anomalies changes from zero to 20 mGal in the case of approaching to source ($h = 3$ km) and increases from -20 mGal to zero in case of passing through a "special points" (Fig.2-3). On the remaining figures in various forms and variants clearly indicate the sources of disturbances (Fig. 4-8). An analytical continuation of the field to the upper half-space to a height of $z = 6$ km was carried out. To do this, the V_z values were calculated at various altitudes, ranging from zero (observation surface) to a height of 6 km with a step of 0.5 km, and as a result a "grid" of the calculated data was obtained, as a result of which various maps in 2D and 3D versions (Fig. 9 -10). As can be seen from the color patterns of the analytical continuation of the field into the upper half-space constructed using the SURFER program, the intensity of the anomalies drops sharply from 5 mGal to 1.2 mGal. And if you subtract this field from the observed on the surface of the earth, you can get the desired local anomaly.

Fig.1. Model of two horizontal cylinders

Fig.2. Analytical continuation of the gravitational field of two silindric bodies in the lower half-space (2D, in units of mGal)

Fig.3. Analytical continuation of the gravitational field of two silindric bodies in the lower half-space (3D, in uits of mGal)

Fig.4. Figurative map of the analytical continuation gravitational field of two silindric bodis in the lower half-space (3D)

Fig.5. Shaded relief map analytic continuation of gravitational fields of two silindric bodis in the upper half-space

Fig.6. Vector map analytic continuation of gravitational fields of two silindric bodies in the upper half-space

Fig.7.

Polar vector map analytic continuation of the gravitational field of two silindric bodis in the lower half-space

Fig.8. Analytic continuation wireframe gravitational field of two cylindrical bodies in the lower half-space (3D)

Fig.9. Analytical continuation of the gravitational field of two silindric bodies in the upper half-space (2D)

Fig.10. Analytical continuation of the gravitational field of two silindric bodis in the upper half-space (3D)

Thus, the conducted studies on analytical continuation of the gravitational field from two silindric bodies, located at a distance closer to each other, show the effectiveness of the analytical continuation of gravimagnetic fields in the allocation of local anomalies associated with promising oil and gas conditions and in direct searches for mineral deposits by the structures of the study area.

Conclusions:

1. A review and analysis of the issues of analytical continuation of the gravitational field into the upper and lower semespaces. The importance and effectiveness of the using of the method of transformation - analytical continuation of the gravitational field for solving the main geological problem of gravity and magnetic exploration is shown.

2. A formula is obtained for calculating the gravitational effect from two-dimensional cylinders located at a close distance from each other at the same depth for use in a graphics program.

3. Using the SURFER program in the “function” mode, based on the transformed formula for calculating the vertical gravity component of a uniform horizontal cylinders lying at a depth of 3 km, the V_z values on the observation surface were calculated and the corresponding grid was subsequently created.

4. The analytical continuation of the model field of a two two-dimensional cylinders into the lower half-space at depths of up to 6 km with a step of 0.5 km was carried out on a computer and V_z maps were built in a modern interface in 2D and 3D versions. The intensity of the anomaly when approaching the source ($h = 3$ km) changes from zero to 20 mGal and increases from -20mGal to zero when passing through a particular point.

5. The analytic continuation of the model field of a two two-dimensional cylinders to the upper half-space to a height of 6 km in steps of 0.5 km was carried out on a computer and the corresponding V_z map was constructed in a modern interface in 2D and 3D versions. The intensity of the anomaly at a distance from the source drops sharply from 5 mGal to 1.2 mGal.

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